

USING READING TEXTS TO DEVELOP VOCABULARY WITH THE SENIOR CLASS LEARNERS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Annotation: *This article discusses about improving senior class learners' vocabulary through reading texts and it includes, as a demand, annotation, keywords, introduction, main part, conclusion and references.*

Keywords: *vocabulary problems, method, technique, short story, language skills, EFL, L2 teachers*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada o'qish matnlari orqali yuqori sinf o'quvchilarining so'z boyligini oshirish haqida so'z boradi va u talab sifatida, izoh, kalit so'zlar, kirish, asosiy qism, xulosa va foydalanilgan adabiyotlarni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *lug'at muammolari, metod, texnika, qisqa hikoya, til ko'nikmalari, EFL, L2 o'qituvchilari*

Аннотация: *В этой статье обсуждается улучшение словарного запаса учащихся старших классов посредством чтения текстов, и она включает, в качестве требования, аннотацию, ключевые слова, введение, основную часть, заключение и список литературы.*

Ключевые слова: *проблемы со словарным запасом, метод, методика, рассказ, языковые навыки, английский язык, английский язык, учителя второго уровня.*

Since vocabulary is considered as one of the most essential part of learning foreign languages, it is imperative for not only learners but also teachers that they should find out a strategy that suits them. The importance

of vocabulary development cannot be overestimated since comprehension is the ultimate goal of reading. A robust vocabulary improves all areas of communication – listening, speaking, reading and writing.

Vocabulary is the most essential component of language teaching for young learners. The teaching of English vocabulary, therefore, plays very important role to enable English as a foreign language (EFL) students to master English. According to Richard and Rodgers (2001), vocabulary is one of the important elements of language proficiency for it is the basis of how well learners speak, write, listen and read. Without a good mastery of vocabulary, learners may be discouraged in using the language being learned in daily activities. Thornbury (2005) characterized that vocabulary holds a crucial position in English. Vocabulary, which is defined by Hornby (2000) as all the words in a particular language or “A list or collection of words and phrases usually alphabetically arranged and explained or defined” (Merriam, 2003), is the main element of language used to inform, to express ideas, to reveal desire and feeling, and to communicate with others. Hammer (2002) accentuated that, “without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary, nothing can be conveyed.” It means that vocabulary is the main element in communication.

To advance learners’ vocabulary, teacher is challenged to improve many kinds of teaching techniques that is useful for a learner to get higher motivation to learn English. One of the teaching techniques that can increase learners’ inspiration in learning English as a foreign language is using a short story. As well as, (Al – Dersi) the use of short stories can be the best method to achieve this goal.

Different studies have proven that using short stories in language learning is quite advantageous as it provides authentic material, cultural enrichment, language advancement, and personal growth. Among the various literary genres, a short story is one of the most appropriate to use in a language classroom.

Short stories are a work of fiction usually written in prose and narrative format and are shorter in length than a novel. According to Wright (2002), “ stories”, in a very broad sense, “ range from full stories in a book to snippets of behavior”, and include “ any descriptions of dramatic events in fact or fiction: traditional stories, local legends, contemporary fiction, the news, personal anecdotes, stories made by students... offered through... personal storytelling, television, theatre, cinema, newspapers, public events” (p. 1). Because it is relatively short, a short story typically focuses on one central theme, one plot, and one major character (with a few supplementary minor characters), whereas a novel can include various plots and themes, with some prominent characters.

Short stories are considered as an exciting and ever – evolving form of storytelling. They talk about the author’s expression towards anything about life experience concerning human imagination. As a literary work, short stories are interesting for people to read and talk. They entertain, develop mental experience and develop learners’ vocabulary. They are also effective to help English learners practice all the four language skills: reading, writing, listening and speaking (Pardede, 2011).

Reading a short story is an necessary process of enhancing learner’s learning capacity and personal development. Furthermore, providing students with a variety of texts that interest them can improve their enjoyment in learning and acts as sufficient motivation to encourage learners to share their personal responses, help in enriching learner’s capability to use English and respond or give expression to real and imaginative experience in their daily life.

There are several new methods which are quite useful for teachers in teaching foreign language. According to Milton (2001), previously conducted studies examining whether presenting students with large amounts of vocabulary might be counterproductive have shown that even the most proficient learner can be overwhelmed by a large amount of new vocabulary

presented, resulting in a lack of learning. Milton (2001) argues that by reducing the amount of words, learning can be improved. Furthermore, it may be of importance for L2 teachers to have a basic knowledge of how the memory and memorization work. By gaining better awareness regarding this, teachers may better maximize the effectiveness of their vocabulary teaching

The National Reading Panel has issued a list consisting of different guidelines that teachers should pay attention to in order to create a multi-faceted leaning environment:

1. Vocabulary should be taught both directly and indirectly.
2. Repetition and multiple exposures to vocabulary items are important.
3. Learning in rich contexts is valuable for vocabulary learning.
4. Vocabulary tasks should be restricted when necessary.
5. Vocabulary learning should entail active engagement in learning tasks.
6. Computer technology can be used to help teach vocabulary.
7. Vocabulary can be acquired through incidental learning.
8. How vocabulary is assessed and evaluated can have differential effects on instruction.
9. Dependence on a single vocabulary instruction method will not result in optimal learning.

(National Reading Panel [NRP], 2000)

The list above shows factors that language teachers need try to keep in mind when structuring their vocabulary teaching. Below, a number of teaching methods being practiced in today's schools are explained.

One of the most widespread method of teaching vocabulary is the use of word-lists. This method provides the students with new vocabulary in a list form. These lists are often connected to a text, providing a context for the words. When working with word-lists one approach is to isolate the words from any context and just provide the translation of the words in question, where the teacher never asks the learners to use the words in a context of a text.

Another effective way of learning vocabulary is through extensive reading. Researchers and teachers agree the fact that reading helps learners to enrich their vocabulary significantly. “ Reading is important, because comparisons of large corpora show that written texts are richer in lexis than spoken ones” (Horst, 2005). According to the National Reading Panel (2000), using extensive reading is considered to be one of the best ways of presenting vocabulary in a rich context. It is argued that by using authentic texts, a more profound vocabulary teaching can be performed then by teaching isolated words without any context.

In conclusion, even though there are so many methods, techniques or approaches improve vocabulary every learner and every teacher should find out the most effective way according to their levels, knowledge and experience.

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